

CHARACTERISATION AND MODELLING OF THE HIGH SPEED PULTRUSION OF COMMINGLED GLASS FIBRE / POLYPROPYLENE COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: A thermoplastic pultrusion line has been developed which is capable of pultruding polypropylene / glass fibre (PP/GF) commingled tows into flat strip and circular rod sections at line speeds up to 10m/min. A heat transfer model was used to predict the temperature profile of the composite at any point during processing allowing for accurate process conditions to be evaluated. A consolidation model has also been developed which can be used to evaluate the effect of pressure and velocity on impregnation conditions. The pultruded sections exhibit good mechanical properties and are of minimal void content. SEM microscopy is used to highlight the impregnation quality of the composites.

KEYWORDS: commingled fibres, thermoplastic composites, pultrusion, consolidation.

INTRODUCTION

For production of a thermoplastic composite it is important that its microstructure is uniformly wetted out and that it has a strong resin/fibre interface [1]. The processing of composites involves impregnating a fibrous bed with resin, then shaping and consolidating it to a high fibre volume fraction. To overcome the design restriction in the forming of complex parts, impregnation can be delayed until the material undertakes its final shape. This *mingling* operation brings the solid polymer and fibre reinforcement together to intimate contact. The aim of this is to reduce the distance the polymer melt must flow in order to fully impregnate the fibre bed. A high degree of intimacy can be achieved by providing the matrix in fibre form and intermingling, or coveaving, polymer fibres with reinforcing fibres. These commingled fibres should ideally be combined in the same strand to minimise the flow distance for impregnation.

Continuous commingled tows are produced when the matrix is spun into a fibre yarn and combined with the reinforcement to produce a commingled hybrid tow. A problem incurred in this route is that intimate mixing is difficult to achieve and may lead to resin rich and unwetted areas of the composite [2]. Therefore, to assure a good distribution of the polymer and reinforcing fibres, it is essential that the matrix fibre diameter is matched as closely as possible to that of the reinforcement [3].

Some workers have recently investigated the potential of commingled fibres for use in the continuous pultrusion process. Michaeli and Jürss [4], claim to have successfully pultruded sectional products such as a strip, a rod and a pipe using a pull braiding system with PP/GF

tows finding that the 'mechanical properties, surface, dimensional and impregnation quality are good, although refinable' but, due to the necessary cooling and consolidation time, high pultrusion speeds were not achieved. Larock *et al* [5], also encountered some difficulties pultruding Graphite/PPS hybrid yarns stating that 'commingled fibres offer unique problems with the initial pultrusion start up'

EXPERIMENTAL

A schematic of the process used for the continuous pultrusion of commingled polypropylene / glass fibres (PP/GF) can be seen in Fig. 1. The process was used to pultrude flat strip and rod sections at line speeds up to 10m/min. The commingled tows were manufactured by Vetrotex under the trade name "Twintex" with 70% by weight (45% by volume) of glass, with an overall tex value of 680. The fibre cheeses were stored on a creel stand and delivered to the process under controlled tension. For production of a 20x2mm rectangular strip 96 tows were used, and for the production of a 2mm diameter rod 8 tows were required. A "bar and plate" tensioning device was used to maintain even tension throughout the system during processing, with uniform pre-tension values varying between 5 and 10 Newtons with line speed.

The pre-tensioned tows then passed through an infra-red oven to preheat the polymer to its melt temperature and initiate wet-out of the reinforcement. The preheat temperatures were dependent on processing speed and thus varied accordingly. The tows were then passed over a series of impregnation pins, a widely accepted technique used to aid the impregnation of thermoplastic matrix composites [6-8]. As the tows travel over the impregnation pins, an applied pressure is generated which increases the polymer melt flow through the reinforcement and reduces the void content of the composite. The tows are then passed through a series of heated forming dies which gradually reduce the product to the required shape. The minimum die contact lengths which are employed in the process preserve a low pull force, which was measured on-line throughout processing using a data acquisition unit. The maximum pull forces measured during processing of the strip varied from 0.375 KN at a line speed of 1m/min to 1.2 KN at 10m/min. Final consolidation and finishing of the product took place in the cold forming die and the finished section consolidated to minimum void content was then spray cooled and hauled off at the end of the process.

In order to understand the cooling and product consolidation stage of the composite, a heat transfer model, derived using finite difference equations, was applied to the process. The model divides the pultruded section into a series of nodes at which the temperature at each point is calculated. This enabled the temperature at any point in the section to be predicted at any position during the pultrusion process. This and the temperature measurements taken on-line were used to define the product and die temperature range where die adhesion ceases and maximum consolidation occurs, allowing for production of composites with minimum void content.

The sections produced from the process were then tested for impregnation quality (void content) using the immersion technique ASTM D-792 and samples were also subjected to the flexural strength test, BS2782 : Pt 3 : Method 335A.

CONSOLIDATION MODELLING

A consolidation model has been developed which can be used to express the degree of consolidation (or reduction in void content) of the composite against pressure and time. This

model can be applied to the pultrusion process and used to determine the optimum pressure and die contact times required to achieve full product consolidation.

The impregnation model should allow for the pressure dependence of impregnation behaviour and the possible power law behaviour of the resin. A flow length, X , can be used to describe the distance (on a microscopic scale) that the resin must flow to achieve the required impregnation level at the end of stage 1 (Fig. 2). For stage 2 a simple model, discussed for instance by Gibson and Månson [9], relates the flow velocity (U) of the resin in the fibre bed by Darcy's law to the pressure gradient from the following equation :

$$U = \frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{SP}{\eta x} \quad (1)$$

The model does not allow for pressure dependence or power law behaviour of the resin. The power law behaviour of the impregnation process was discussed by Aström *et al* [10] who proposed the following equation :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{k'}{Y} \left(\frac{P}{x} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (2)$$

where n is the power law index and k' and Y are constants. If k' is a function of pressure then,

$$k' = AP^{-m} \quad (3)$$

where A and m are constants. Substituting eqn. (2) into (3) produces the following :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = \frac{A}{Y} \frac{P^{\frac{1}{n}-m}}{x^{\frac{1}{n}}} \quad (4)$$

which can be expressed as

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = B \frac{P^{\frac{1}{n}-m}}{x^{\frac{1}{n}}} \quad (5)$$

where B is constant from A and Y .

Constant velocity conditions

A series of compaction trials were undertaken to investigate the consolidation behaviour of the commingled material. Layers of material were stacked together in a matched die mould at a temperature of 190°C and compressed at 5, 20, 50 and 100mm/min as shown in Fig. 3. The variation of pressure versus flow length was measured during each test, until the samples were consolidated to minimum void content. For these constant velocity conditions the cross head speed, V is related to eqn. (5) below,

$$V = B \frac{P^{\frac{1}{n}-m}}{x^{\frac{1}{n}}} \quad (6)$$

therefore

$$V^n x = B^n P^{(1-nm)} \quad (7)$$

Plotting P versus $V^n x$ varying n until the curves close together is shown in Fig. 4 for a value of $n = 0.25$. Taking a Log - Log plot of this gives the graph shown in Fig. 5 in which the slope approximates to 1. It can therefore be said that, to a good approximation, $m = 0$. So from this,

$$V = B \left(\frac{P}{x} \right)^{\frac{1}{n}} \quad (8)$$

The value of B can be found from the graph and is equal to 0.14.

Constant pressure conditions

Constant pressure conditions occur during the pultrusion process as the tow passes over the impregnation pins. Since $m = 0$ we know from eqn. (5) that :

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = B \frac{P^{\frac{1}{n}}}{x^{\frac{1}{n}}} \quad (9)$$

Rearranging we obtain,

$$x^{\frac{1}{n}} dx = BP^{\frac{1}{n}} dt \quad (10)$$

Integrating this expression gives

$$\frac{n}{n+1} x^{\frac{n+1}{n}} + C = BP^{\frac{1}{n}} t \quad (11)$$

and since when $x = 0$, $t = 0$ so $C = 0$, so the time for consolidation under constant pressure conditions can be expressed as :

$$t = \left(\frac{n}{n+1} \right) \frac{x^{\frac{n+1}{n}}}{BP^{\frac{1}{n}}} \quad (12)$$

where $n = 0.25$ and $B = 0.14$. The results from this model can then be compared to the experimental conditions observed during pultrusion processing, where a constant pressure is observed.

Variation of void content initial conditions

The variation of void content against impregnation level can be found from the unit volume of material described in Fig. 2. At the initial condition, before any resin flow has taken place, the flow length, x , is equal to zero. As the volume of fibres is equal to V_{f1} , the same as at the end conditions, the volume of matrix will be equal to $1 - V_{f1}$ which is also the same as the end conditions. Thus the volume of voids occupied at the initial condition will also be equal to $1 - V_{f1}$, which is the volume that will eventually be occupied by the matrix. The total unit volume can therefore be written as :

$$\text{Total unit volume} = 2 - V_{f1} \quad (13)$$

where the initial void volume fraction, V_{v0} , is given by :

$$V_{v0} = \frac{1 - V_{f1}}{2 - V_{f1}} \quad (14)$$

which, for a 45% by volume of glass commingled composite is equal to 0.35.

Variation of void content - intermediate conditions

As the resin flows a distance x (Fig.2) the degree of impregnation, x^* , is defined as x/X . The volume of voids occupied at this stage can be expressed as

$$\text{Volume of voids} = (1 - V_{f1})(1 - x^*) \quad (15)$$

Therefore the intermediate void fraction will follow this relationship :

$$V_v = \frac{(1 - V_{f1})(1 - x^*)}{1 + (1 - V_{f1})(1 - x^*)} \quad (16)$$

At the end condition $x^* = 1$, which is the condition of full impregnation, where $V_v = 0$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Pultrusion processing results

The graph shown in Fig.6 represents the comparison between measured and theoretical void content reduction against impregnation time for the pultrusion of a 20x2mm commingled PP/GF strip at a line speed of 1m/min. The modelled impregnation time (solid line) was calculated from eqn. (12) in which the theoretical reduction in void content was calculated from eqn. (16).

The average pressure induced as the tows passed over the impregnation pins was constant for each line speed and calculated from

$$P = \frac{T}{2rw} \quad (17)$$

where T is the tension in the tows (measured pull force during processing), r the impregnation pin radius and w the tow width as it passes over the pins. Thus for a line speed of 1m/min the average pull force was measured to be 375N and with a pin radius of 15mm and tow width of 40mm, an average pressure over the pins of 0.312MPa was achieved. The experimental data points were taken as the tow passed over each pin and were measured using the immersion technique ASTM D-792. It can be seen from the graph that the results correlate well with the models predictions. The minimum void content achievable through pin impregnation was found to be 8%. The void content was then further reduced to a minimum value as it passed through the consolidation dies further down the process.

Mechanical properties results

The mechanical properties in relation quality and line speed were measured in terms of flexural strength for the pultruded sections of a 20 x 2mm strip and 2mm diameter rod section. Figs 7 and 8 show that the mechanical properties are slightly reduced as the line speed is increased, due to the reduction in impregnation time and increase in void content. The final void content values were found to vary between 0 and 2% for speeds 1 to 5m/min and from 1 to 4% for speeds 5 to 10m/min. The values of flexural strength for both sections are good varying between 600 - 700 MPa according to these conditions. Fig. 9 shows the SEM micrograph of a 20x2mm strip pultruded at 7m/min. The impregnation level is seen to be good, with few dark areas observed which demonstrates the minimum void content of the composite.

CONCLUSIONS

A consolidation model has been applied to commingled fibres which relates impregnation time to pressure and velocity and can be used to predict optimum conditions for pultrusion processing. The pultrusion line developed can successfully produce continuous sections of strip and rod with minimum void content and good mechanical properties at high line speeds. The results demonstrate that the pultrusion of commingled fibres is a promising technique in the development of thermoplastic composites and now that the base technology is established, more complex shapes can be attempted in the future.

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Fig. 1 : Schematic of the process used to pultrude continuous commingled PP/GF tows into product sections

Fig. 2 : Impregnation of a porous fibre bed under an applied pressure, P .

Fig. 3 : Consolidation of commingled tows at various compaction rates

Fig. 4 : Plot of Pressure (MPa) versus $V^n x$, where $n = 0.25$

Fig. 5 : Plot of $\text{Log}(P)$ versus $\text{Log}(V^n x)$, slope ~ 1

Fig. 6 : Consolidation results for a 20 x 2mm strip pultruded at 1m/min. The solid line represents the theoretical values obtained from eqn(12) and the points represent experimental data

Fig. 7 : Flexural strength versus line speed for a pultruded 20 x 2mm strip

Fig. 8 : Flexural strength versus line speed for a pultruded 2mm diameter rod

Fig. 9 : SEM micrograph of a pultruded 20x2mm strip produced at a line speed of 7m/min.